

doi:10.5281/zenodo.20027691

Evaluation Of The Funding And Management In Public Secondary School In Potiskum Educational Zone Yobe State, Nigeria

¹Musa Yusuf Mohammed; ²Mohammed Ahmed & ³Ahmed S. Fada

¹Department of Social Studies

Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

²Department of History

Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

³Department of Hausa

Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This research work is aimed to determine the sources and management of funds of public secondary schools in Potiskum educational zones. The research used descriptive survey and the population comprise four categories of participants which include principals of the selected schools. The data collected was analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistic. Statistical package for social science will be employed to analysed the data. Results of the study showed that issuing receipts for all monies collected from parents, students etc, involving sectional and departmental heads in budget preparation; rendering financial reports to the Post-primary school management board, among others, are ways to manage school funds. The state government and owners of private schools should provide secondary schools with appropriate money or open a bank account for the schools where the funds can be properly kept.

Keywords: management of fund, public secondary schools, principals

INTRODUCTION

The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) has identified broad goals of secondary education to include the following: preparation of students for useful living within the society, preparation for higher education, equip students to live effectively in our modern age of science and technological development, project Nigeria culture, art and language as well as the world's culture, foster Nigerian unity with emphasis on common ties that unit us in our diversity, inspire the students with the achievement of self-improvement both at school and in later life. One of the major determinant of qualitative education is adequate funding. The objectives of secondary education cannot be achieved without effective principals. The kind of education that it provided for children after primary education, prior to tertiary education. The importance of secondary education in educational system cannot be overemphasized. Though it serves as a hinge between primary and tertiary education, it equally provides opportunity for a child to acquire additional knowledge, skills and value beyond the primary level, Ekpo (2017).

Aghenta, 2000 described management can be defined as the process of organizing, planning, leading, measuring and controlling as well as undertaking of risks and handling of uncertainly, planning and innovation; coordination and routine supervision. It is a process designed to ensure the co-operation, participation intervention and involvement of people in the effective achievement of a given objective (Fabunmi, 2000). It is also a social process concerned with identifying, maintaining, motivation, controlling and unifying formally and information organized human and material resources (with a system (Musaazi, 1982). In such a social process, there is always a structural hierarchy comprising the subordinates and Super-ordinates. Management of funds therefore deals with the provision, custody and disbursement of the financial resources needed for the running of public, private or government established schools.

Effective and accurate financial management is necessary in the school institution to avoid financial mismanagement. In a place where the principal is weak and ineffective in managing the resources of the school, success will be very difficult to achieve. Financial management is one of the tasks of the school principals. Ezeocha (1990) stated that “whether a school principal has a bursar or not he has the duty of seeing that adequate financial provision is made in the school budget. He also noted that effective management demands that budget proposals be prepared before any new session. Ozigi (1981) stated that the greatest problem militating and facing the educational institutions is the inappropriate management of funds.

The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) acknowledges education as a vehicle for national development. The achievement of educational goals of any nation depends largely on adequate financial support. The funding and prudent management of scarce resources in secondary schools are crucial issues, which should be handled with all amounts of seriousness. The principal of secondary school is therefore the fundamental person upon whom the resource utilization of the school organization depends. Management of funds in educational organization like secondary schools have been a very sensitive and controversial issue because it exposes the strengths and weakness of those entrusted to manage the fund. Okoke (2005), explained that basic requirements as infrastructures that include buildings, classrooms, laboratories, workshops, administrative blocks, furniture, and work benches are necessary. Invariably, funds are needed to properly put all these basic requirements in place. Funding here, refers to the sum of money budgeted for a period for educational purpose. It is government’s responsibility to provide financial needs based on top priority as government can and ought to respond to the public secondary schools. Funding of education has drawn the attention of many educationists and scholars as education is seen as a major user of economic resources. The process of impacting education is either done through facilitators or teachers in designated school facilities following planned learning activities done to achieve stated educational goals.

Again Ogbonnaya (2000) sees the financing of education as the methodology whereby tax money and other resources are derived for the upgrading of educational facilities and inputs in a state. This is done by establishing and operating of educational institutions based on the process by which resources are allocated to institutions sited in different location. The sources of fund include both short and long term which can be explained; thus, short term sources of funds include school fees, Parents Teachers Association levies, and approved levies by the government, sales of locally produced items such as proceeds from the school farm and voluntary donations. Such monies are needed for short period of time that can be identified from between one to six months. Such funds are normally raised within the shortest possible period and could be very useful to educational institutions. Short term sources of funds can be classified into two; internal and external. Anyanwu (1997), further stated that money saved and made are normally available for purposes. In other cases, it can be referred to as physical cash, credit facilities which may be trade credits; bank credits allowances or discounts received. All others differed as an expense that include differed taxes, rents, and rates bills and undistributed profits that the forms of retained earnings, reserves, depreciation, and provisions. Anyanwu (1997), explained that internal funds include retained earnings, depreciation provisions and accounts payable. Others are new equity and possible proceeds from states of assets. Further identified external sources to include those outside the

educational institutions that required contact with external bodies such as United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural organization (UNESCO), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the World Bank and exchange programmes undertaken by different institutions.

As identified by Ogunu (2000), grants as assistance given by federal, state or local government authorities to schools that are worth receiving such grants that is, those who meet conditions precedent to such benefits. Previous examples demonstrated include; community self-help projects that may have been allocated to institutions depending on some factors; size of the institution, number of students enrolled and needs of the school recognized by the granting organization. The long-term sources of funding include grants, endowment, and other donations. Grants are seen as possible sources of fund in educational programmes here in Nigeria.

The fact that in recent times, economic recessions have made allocations from federal, state, and local government to schools to decline as expressed by Yoleye (1994). This has reduced revenue proportion allocated to different levels of education especially secondary and higher institutions. This can apply in controlling and directing all funding, subventions, grants as well as other funding coming in with strings attached. Therefore, the methodology of channeling funds can be directed solely through administrative machinery that accounts for taxpayers money. He states that the involvement of the federal government in almost all facets of educational funding directs how money is spent and raises a few questions that include the following: Is it proper that the financial burden in education be shifted from the state to parents? Can the direct link with the grassroots provide a lasting solution to the control and methodology of how finances are raised and channeled to schools? Is localism providing a final answer since administrative decentralization within local governments function well in a democratic system? It can be recognized that the more people can be granted power since government is closer to the people, people can be granted power since government is closer to the people can be more conscious of what obtains in the school environment. this can include payment of taxation, rising of bonds for school projects and getting more involved in Parents - Teachers' activities that may raise and fund schools' ventures.

Effectiveness of the principals' administration is often determined by the extent to which teachers do their work well and the extent to which students achieve the goals of instructions in school and how they perform in external examinations and other extracurricular activities (Marion 2004). Moreover, the management of secondary schools is an onerous task of the principals. The principals are the pivots around which all major and important school activities resolve. This means that, the managerial qualities that principals bring to their work have far-reaching impact on how the overall enterprise of the school is done. For instance, a successful principal, according to Amahi (2006) should be honest, objective, have self-control, adaptable and self-confident in his day-to-day activities. A principal who wants to inspire honest in teachers or spirits of hard work must himself show these traits.

Objectives of the study

The following are the objectives of the study.

1. Assessing the funding of public secondary schools through government grants and how the funds generated are managed in Potiskum educational zones.
2. Determining the funding of public secondary schools through the school fees and how the funds generated are managed in Potiskum educational zones.

Statement of the Problems

Ogbonnaya (2000) observed that poor management of funds in secondary schools has created a lot of lapses, which have affected the achievement of the desired educational goals. The principals on their own part blame the government for poor funding of secondary schools, inadequate supply of capital equipment and instructional materials, among others. Funding of education has drawn the attention of many educationists and scholars as education is seen as a major user of economic resources. The process of impacting education is either done through facilitators or teachers in designated school facilities following planned learning activities done to achieve stated educational goals.

Research Questions

Three research questions are used to guide this research study. They include:

- i) How does the principals source funds in secondary schools in Potiskum Educational zone?
- ii) What factors affects the financial management practices of principals in Potiskum Educational zone?

METHODOLOGY

The design of this study was descriptive survey, this seeks to establish the opinion of the principals of junior and senior secondary schools in Potiskum Educational Zone, Yobe state on funding and management of some public secondary schools (i.e sources of fund generation, budget preparation, disbursement of funds and how funds are accounted for. The population of the study comprises of some selected principals of government financed junior and senior secondary schools in Potiskum Educational zone in yobe state. This was considered adequate for the study. The researcher used mean and standard deviation to analyze the research questions, and t-test to test formulated hypotheses. For the research questions 2.50 was used as the criterion mean. Any item that attains a response mean score of 2.50 and above was accepted otherwise it was rejected.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: There will be no significant difference between the mean rating of junior secondary schools and senior secondary school principals on the sources of funding secondary schools in Potiskum Educational Zone, Yobe State.

S/NO	Items	No.	Mean	SD	df	tcal	tcritical	Decision
1	Senior Principals	6	2.65	1.41	8	0.86	1.96	Accepted
2	Junior Principals	2	2.87	0.96				

The hypothesis is accepted because at 0.05 level of significance, with 8 degrees of freedom, the critical value is 1.96 which is higher than calculated t-value (0.86). This shows that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of junior and senior secondary school principals on sources of funds for selected secondary schools in the study area.

Hypothesis 2: There will be no significant difference between the mean rating of junior secondary schools and senior secondary school principals on the financial management of secondary schools in Potiskum Educational Zone, Yobe State.

S/NO	Items	No.	Mean	SD	df	tcal	tcritical	Decision
1	Senior Principals	6	2.77	1.15	8	1.41	1.96	Significant
2	Junior Principals	2	2.63	1.08				

The table above shows that the calculated t-value of 1.41 at 8 degrees of freedom also at 0.05 level of significance the t-value is 1.96. Since the calculated t-value of 1.41 is less than the table value of 1.96, the null hypothesis is accepted. This signifies that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of junior and senior secondary school principals on financial management in selected secondary schools in the study area.

CONCLUSION

Education is a collective responsibility of all stakeholders. Therefore, the school principal is expected to complement governments' effort by diversifying their income bases and utilizing the available funds judiciously for the attainment of their organizational goals. Moreover, a situation where school principals do not employ accountability in their financial management practices implies a hazardous condition in such schools. The quality of education made accessible for the public would depend largely on the pattern of resource management in our schools. This implies that there is a direct relationship between the quality of instructional facilities provided and the managerial practices employed by school administrators. The problem of shortage of qualified teachers and lack of instructional facilities do not exclusively rest on funding as often depicted, rather the problems are made complex due to poor management. One can therefore conclude that principals in Kaduna State should perform their financial management duties in a manner satisfactory enough to enhance sustainable development of secondary schools. Hence, secondary school principals should seek for innovative practices such as training in ICT, accounting, internal auditing, prompt disbursement of funds, and implementation of budget to enhance sustainable management of secondary education in Potiskum educational zone, yobe State.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This is to acknowledge the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (Tetfund) for funding this research through the Institutional Based Research (IBR) of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State.

REFERENCES

- Abass, A. (2003). Public Record and Information Management in 21 Century. In Management of Public Record and Information Materials in Local Administration, Lagos: NIREM, Pg. 23.
- Abubakar, S.H. (2008). Educational Research; A comprehensive Guide to Amodu students. Kano Sk. Printing and Publishing House.
- Adeleke, T. (2010). Effective Schools and Quality Improvement lesson with Direct support Schools mechanism Nairobi: Government printer.
- Akpa (2008) Financial management practices of primary school heads in Udi education zone of Enugu state M.ED thesis Department of Educational Foundation Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.
- Enyi, D. (2001) Strategies for Community Involvement in Funding Nigeria's Primary Educations: A Case Study of Kaduna State. *Journal of Anambra State Education (JOPED)*. 2. (1), 2-12. International Limited.
- Lewi (2006). Expanded Access to Secondary Schooling in Sub-Saharan Africa: Key Planning and Finance issues, Commissioned Position paper: London. DFID
- Marion, M. (2004). Time and Self-management for personal effectiveness. *Management in Nigeria Journal*.
- Obanya P. (2002). Guideline for realizing Nigeria millennium education Dream: The UBE paper presented at a seminar on Stakeholders in UBE. Abuja, September 17th -20th.
- Ofougwuka, A. (2005). An appraisal of the role achievement of PTA in Secondary School Administration in Anambra State. An M.Ed. Thesis submitted to the Department of Education foundations. Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka
- Ogbonnaya, N. (2005) Education Finance. Onitsha: cape publishers.
- Oguonu, C.N. (2007) Financial and Administrative control in Secondary schools, in
- Ezeze, C.C Nigerian Journal Public Administration and Local Government. Vol. 8, No.1.
- Osuala, E.C. (2007). Foundation of Vocational Education. Onitsha, Nigeria; Cape Publishers.
- Pandey, I.M. (1995). Financial Management. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House Limited.
- San – Luis, J. (2007). The Delivery of Social Service: A Case in Philippine Public Education Quezon City. Department of Education. Retrieved on 6th October 2007 <http://smhp.pstch.ucla.edu/pdfocs>.
- UNDP (2006). Global development report. Retrieved on 12th June 2008 FROM <http://www.qualelearning.net/>.